

1 **C1RL is differentially expressed in glioblastoma.**

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6 Glioblastoma is difficult to treat and patients are often provided poor prognosis (1), indicating a
7 requirement for therapeutic target identification and drug development. Differentially expressed genes
8 represent by definition among the most promising targets for the development of novel chemotherapies (2,
9 3). We predict therapeutic index is intrinsically linked to differential expression which can be
10 comprehensively and blindly determined using whole transcriptome data, further limiting toxicity by
11 design (4). We mined published and public microarray and RNA-sequencing data (5, 6) to identify
12 differentially expressed gene products in glioblastoma by performing whole transcriptome gene expression
13 profiling. We found that the gene encoding the complement component 1, r subcomponent-like, C1RL,
14 was among those whose expression was most different in human glioblastoma tumors when comparing
15 total transcription between tumor and normal brain tissue. C1RL expression levels were significantly
16 increased in glioblastoma tumors as compared to the non-transformed brain. C1RL function at the systems
17 level was assessed by studying whole transcriptome transcriptional co-regulation in the transformed brain.
18 C1RL is a target of interest for the treatment of glioblastoma, as part of a rationally designed
19 chemotherapeutic regimen that utilizes gene expression data from patient tumors and healthy
20 non-transformed tissues to maximize efficacy and safety and minimize toxicity.

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26 Keywords: C1RL, complement component 1, r subcomponent-like, glioblastoma, systems biology of
27 glioblastoma, targeted therapeutics in glioblastoma.

1 Brain cancer encompasses a spectrum of solid tumors that affect the brain in children and adults
2 including medulloblastoma, neuroblastoma, and glioblastoma (7). Rational development of targeted
3 therapeutics to treat patients with glioblastoma can be supported by an enhanced understanding of
4 fundamental transcriptional differences that define the glioblastoma tumor. To discover genes associated
5 with glioblastoma in humans in an unbiased fashion and at the systems level, we compared total
6 transcription in the normal brain and in the glioblastoma tumor using published and public human
7 glioblastoma microarray and RNA-sequencing data (5, 6) to identify a molecular signature or fingerprint
8 of glioblastoma, among the most lethal and difficult to treat solid tumors affecting adults. We describe
9 here identification of a potential therapeutic target in glioblastoma based on quantitative whole
10 transcriptome methods.

11 **Methods**

12 We utilized microarray datasets GSE116520 (5) and GSE184643 (6) for this differential gene
13 expression analysis of the brain cancer glioblastoma in humans using R-based computational methods
14 (GEO2R). GSE116520 was generated using Illumina HumanHT-12 V4.0 expression beadchip
15 technology; for this analysis, we used $n=8$ control brain tissue and $n=17$ glioblastoma tumors, and the
16 analysis was performed using platform GPL10558. GSE184643 was generated using Illumina NovaSeq
17 6000 (Homo sapiens) technology; for this analysis, we used $n=3$ control brain tissue and $n=3$ glioblastoma
18 tumors, and the analysis was performed using platform GPL24676. All tumors utilized for differential
19 gene expression analysis here were of the adenocarcinoma type. The Benjamini and Hochberg method of
20 p-value adjustment was used for ranking of differential expression but raw p-values were used to assess
21 statistical significance of global differential expression. Log-transformation of data was auto-detected, and
22 the NCBI generated category of platform annotation was used. SEEK was utilized for transcriptional
23 co-regulation studies (8).

24 **Results**

25 We harnessed the power of whole transcriptome technologies and cross-laboratory validation (5, 6)
26 to discover in an unbiased fashion and at the transcriptome level the most distinguishing gene expression
27 features of the human brain cancer glioblastoma.

28 C1RL is differentially expressed in glioblastoma.

1. Primary tumors of the brain from humans with glioblastoma

$n=8$ normal brain tissues (human)

$n=17$ primary tumors (brain; human; glioblastoma)

ID	p-value	t	B	logFC	Gene	Rank	%DE
ILMN_1733288	4.24E-04	-3.831656	-0.539551	-0.87121874	C1RL	8627/47229	81.7

29 Through quantitative comparison of total transcription in normal brain tissues and glioblastoma
30 tumor tissue, we discovered differential expression of complement component 1, r subcomponent-like,
31 encoded by C1RL in glioblastoma in humans (**Chart 1**). The expression of C1RL changed more than
32 80% of the human brain and brain tumor transcriptome when considering all transcripts whose expression
33 was measured - in this case, 47,229 transcripts ("Rank"). Note the negative fold-change

1 indicating increased quantity of C1RL messenger RNA in glioblastoma tumors, demonstrating
 2 up-regulation of C1RL during transformation of the brain from normal brain tissue to glioblastoma.

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 4 2. Primary tumors of the brain from humans with brain cancer: glioblastoma.

5 $n=3$ normal brain tissues (human)

6 $n=3$ primary tumors (brain; human; glioblastoma)

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ID	p-value	lfcSE	stat	log2FoldChange	baseMean	Gene	Rank	%DE
51279	3.15E-06	0.461	-4.6605555	-2.15014655	385.89	C1RL	987/19678	94.9

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9 Through quantitative comparison of total transcription in normal brain tissues and glioblastoma
 10 tumors in a second RNA-sequencing dataset from independent investigators and a separate patient cohort,
 11 we validated differential expression of C1RL in glioblastoma in humans (**Chart 2**). The expression of
 12 C1RL here changed more than 95% of the human brain and brain tumor transcriptome when considering
 13 all transcripts whose expression was measured - in this case, 19,678 transcripts (“Rank”). Note the
 14 negative fold-change indicating increased quantity of C1RL messenger RNA in glioblastoma tumors,
 15 demonstrating up-regulation of C1RL during transformation of the brain from normal brain tissue to
 16 glioblastoma.

17 Thus, C1RL is a gene whose differential expression defines the transcriptional landscape of the
 18 glioblastoma subtype in humans.

19 C1RL transcriptional co-regulation.

20 Finally, we utilized a separate systems methodology that utilizes whole transcriptome data to
 21 provide insight into molecular function of a gene product by evaluating the transcriptional network within
 22 which it operates through identification of co-regulated gene partners.

27 In the transformed brain, C1RL was transcriptionally co-regulated with C1R, C1S, CFI, CFB,
 28 CD44, ABCC3 CASP1 and TNFRSF1A.

1 Thus, blind comparative transcriptome analysis of glioblastomas revealed differential expression of
2 C1RL as among the most significant transcriptional features of glioblastoma tumors; systems level query
3 into C1RL molecular function across multiple tissues at the transcriptome level revealed its co-regulation
4 with C1R, C1S, CFI, CFB, CD44, ABCC3 CASP1 and TNFRSF1A.

4 **Discussion**

5 We found by mining published and public microarray and RNA-sequencing data (5, 6) that the
6 complement component 1, r subcomponent-like, C1RL, was among the genes most differentially
7 expressed in the primary tumors of patients with glioblastoma; C1RL was expressed at significantly higher
8 levels in glioblastoma tumors as compared to the brain. C1RL is a target of interest for the understanding
9 of rationally designed medical treatment of glioblastoma, a difficult to treat adult solid tumor.
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